

SPECIFIC ASPECTS OF ORGANIZING PHYSICAL TRAINING AND SPORTS EVENTS IN THE HIGHER EDUCATION SYSTEM

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Abstract. This article describes in detail the specific aspects of the organization of physical education and sports events in the higher education system.

Keywords: physical training, students, higher education, sports clubs, morning physical education, etc.

The purpose of teaching features in the course of physical education and sports training is to teach pupils and students the requirements for physical development of the body and a healthy lifestyle. At the same time, physical training, sports and wellness activities will greatly help to master professional training. Pupils and students' physical education activities are in the form of morning physical education, physical education classes, sports club training, sports fitness competitions and holidays. Morning physical education classes are held in public in student dormitories and independently in residence halls and families. The scientific work is one of the first to be done today. It analyzes the importance of physical education and sports and health activities of pupils and students in raising the young generation as a well-rounded person. Forms of improvement of this process are studied. Physical education activities in educational institutions consist of physical development, health and preparation of pupils and students for life activities. Physical education processes are organized at all stages. In the organization of physical education, the pedagogical team of the educational institution, physical education teachers and sports coaches are of

great importance. Physical education activities in educational institutions are morning physical education, physical education classes, training in sports clubs, sports competitions and tourism activities conducted on holidays and weekends. In the physical education activities, the students' movement skills and abilities are formed by performing the vital activities of walking, running, jumping, throwing, and climbing. Positive changes occur and the body becomes healthy with the help of physical exercises and the healing forces of nature, as well as hygienic tools, which are considered as physical education tools.

The law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Public Education" and "On Physical Education and Sports" states that citizens of the Republic of Uzbekistan must take care of their physical training in order to improve and strengthen their health. is keyed. This law fully applies to physical education in schools. Physical education of pupils and students is an organized pedagogical process of their physical activities. Physical education activities in an educational institution differ in very diverse forms that require enthusiasm, initiative, and organization from pupils and students. They help to educate pupils and students in organizational skills, activity and resourcefulness. Providing special knowledge about physical exercises and sports. Physical exercise is understood as a different set of voluntary movement activities that meet the requirements of the laws of physical education and are performed consciously. Such movement activities were historically systematized, collected, and filled with style as gymnastics, games, sports, and tourism exercises. To teach them hygienic knowledge and skills. This task is to provide students with the necessary knowledge about the benefits of physical training, hygiene rules, and the rules for correct performance of all physical exercises provided for in the program. All of these are directly related to health promotion, their knowledge of hygiene rules and their adherence to them, and this is achieved by the joint action of the school, family, community and children themselves. Physical exercises and sports are taught in physical education classes,

daily activities and club activities. As a result, physical development is ensured. Also, pupils and students are interested in sports and are attracted to sports. Strengthening health, helping students to develop and train properly. Under the influence of natural factors, water, sun, air, students' health will be strengthened, trained, and the body will be more resistant to diseases. Carrying out physical education classes in fresh air as much as possible or organizing sports halls with fresh air. Leading pupils and students in water treatments, swimming and bathing activities, and sunbathing activities. These activities are carried out during walks, excursions and tourism activities. This task is considered the most important of all physical culture and sports activities in an educational institution. It should be the center of attention of every teacher and team of pedagogues. Therefore, pupils and students should develop normally from a physical point of view.

Formation and improvement of movement, skills and abilities, training in new movement types and movement activities. The content of the physical culture program of pupils and students is structured in such a way that students regularly engage in physical culture classes, at home, in physical culture clubs and sports clubs, and perform life-necessary movements such as walking, running, throwing, crawling, and balancing. acquire skills systematically. All the listed activities will help in all-round physical development and preparation for cocktails. In the formation of movement skills and abilities of pupils and students, it is necessary to approach them according to their gender, age, physical fitness and personal abilities. Improvement of physical qualities. Speed, strength, dexterity and endurance and flexibility are qualities that everyone needs. They are inextricably linked with the formation of movement skills in pupils and students. Carrying out physical exercises for a short or long time at different speeds and with different complications helps to develop the above qualities. Development of physical qualities in accordance with each other. Organizing classes according to the personal abilities of the participants and involving students in sports. Education of

mental and aesthetic qualities. Cultivating bravery, determination, discipline, community, sense of friendship and camaraderie, cultural behavior skills, attitude to work and social property. The whole process of physical education helps to cultivate such valuable moral and willful qualities. Many physical exercises and play activities help to cultivate the qualities of kindness and friendship. Also, formation and upbringing of love for the Motherland, patriotism, feelings. Forming the right figure. Forming the skills to maintain the correct posture while standing and walking. Correct formation of the figure is a complex and long-lasting process. Therefore, in order to achieve positive results in this area, it is advisable to maintain a correct posture when standing and walking; physical exercises should be widely used; It is necessary to include in the content of physical culture classes exercises related to height improvement, pre-class gymnastics, physical culture times, physical education, pupils and students should constantly work on themselves with physical and mental exercises, and give homework. It is expected to achieve results on the basis of timely checking and practical testing of assigned tasks. Educating pupils and students in a wide range of mental and moral aspects is one of the most important tasks, because the consciousness of pupils and students is during development.

Involvement in physical education and sports activities. It is to accustom pupils and students to systematic physical exercises not only in educational institutions, but also at home. In order to fulfill this important task, all activities conducted with pupils and students should be lively, the content and form of the studied material should be interesting, exciting, conducted under the sincere treatment of the leader of the activity, the participants should interact with each other. It is necessary to create conditions for cooperation. To attract pupils and students to engage in sports according to their personal interests and physical abilities. Also, it is necessary to carry out general physical training and sports training in the places of residence and sports clubs. Education of organization in

pupils and students, preparation of physical culture activities. In order to successfully carry out public physical culture and sports activities in the educational institution, to conduct physical culture classes and trainings in full, students and students need the constant support of the teacher of physical culture activities.

References:

1. SH.M. Mirziyoyev «Buyuk kelajagimizni mard va oliyanob xalqimiz bilan birga quramiz» 2018 T:
2. O`zbekiston Respublikasining «Jismoniy tarbiya va sport to`g`risidagi qonun»gi. , -T.:O`zbekiston. 2015 4-sentyabr
3. SH.M. Mirziyoyev O`zbekiston Respublikasida jismoniy tarbiya va ommaviy sportni yanada rivojlantirish chora tadbirlari to`g`risidagi 2017-yil 3-iyundagi PQ-3031-son [qarori](#).
4. Jismoniy tarbiya va ommaviy sportni rivojlantirish to`g`risidagi Konsepsiya 2019 13-fevral.
5. Haydarov B.T., Ibroimova G.X. “Jismoniy tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi” (Maktabgacha ta`lim tashkilotlarida) “SamDU” nashri o`quv qo`llanma. 2020 y.
6. Haydarov B.T., Eshtayev A.K.Ibroimova G.X. “Maktabgacha ta`lim tashkilotlarida gimnastika mashg`ulotlarini o`tkazish usullari” “SamDU” nashri o`quv-uslubiy qo`llanma. 2019 y.
7. Haydarov B.T., Ibroimova G.X. “Maktabgacha ta`lim tashkilotlarida Jismoniy tarbiya nazariyasi” “SamDU” nashri darslik. 2020 y.